

Extrapolation Capabilities Of Data Driven Methods In Combustion LES

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Introduction:

- Data driven models are increasingly used in combustion and LES.
- Applications: SGS modelling, Chemical kinetics, surrogate, etc...

Data driven methods:

Point Regression Methods (*PRM*)

- Only local information
- e.g., Random Forests, Artificial Neural Network, etc...
- Easier to integrate into CFD solvers

Field Regression Methods (*FRM*)

- Has information of the immediate region
- e.g., CNNs, PointNet, etc...
- Complex to integrate into CFD solvers

Data driven methods:

Objective:

- Which methods can **extrapolate** well **beyond training data** distribution?
across combustion LES relevant **conditions**

Why?

- **Training** data (DNS) is **costly** → only limited training data
- **Integration** into **CFD** solvers is **non-trivial** → Does it justify the cost and effort?

How?

Dataset

a) Slot burner
Premixed H₂-Air
 $\phi = 0.45$ [1]

b) Freely propagating flame Vitiated H₂ Air
combustion
BlastNet.io [2] → for Karlovitz comparison

DNS data

Filtering,
Favre
averaging,
Sampling to
coarser grid

LES like field

Preprocessing,
sampling, etc

Data driven
model training

Data driven method:

Methods objective:

Data driven methods:

Point Regression Methods

PRMs

- Random Forest - *RF*
- Multi Layer Perceptron - *MLP*
- Kolmogorov Arnold Networks - *KAN*

vs

Field Regression Methods

FRMs

- Convolutional Neural network - *CNN*
- UNet

Conditions evaluated

- I. Karlovitz number
- II. Equivalence ratios

- III. Mesh resolution
- IV. Thickened Flame fields
- V. Inflow velocity (U_{in}/SL)

Results

I. Karlovitz (Ka) extrapolation:

Data: Freely propagating H2 flame

Trained: low ka flame

Tested: Upto $Ka = 15 * ka_{train}$

- All methods show similar MAE.
- A different pattern in truth vs prediction distributions for PRMs

Ka extrapolation: FRM

- FRM methods extrapolate well to higher Ka flames

Ka extrapolation: PRM

- A cutoff is seen beyond which RF doesn't predict values

Ka extrapolation

$$\bar{\Sigma} > \max(\bar{\Sigma}_{train})$$

$$Ka = 15 * ka_{train}$$

- A similar cut off is seen across all point regression methods
- This point relates to maximum value in training distribution
- PRM methods → poor extrapolation to higher Ka flames

II. Equivalence ratio:

Trained: $\phi = 0.45$
Tested: $\phi = 0.7$ & 0.35

- All models extrapolate to higher $\phi = 0.7$,
- PRMs **underpredict** at leaner flames, $\phi = 0.35$ - **18% lower** on average \rightarrow why?

Plot: Integrated flame density ($\bar{\Sigma}$) along X

Equivalence ratio

Plot: Truth ($\bar{\Sigma}_{DNS}^*$) Vs Prediction ($\bar{\Sigma}_{NN}^*$) at $\phi = 0.35$

FRMs

PRMs

Similar pattern across all PRMs

Equivalence ratio

PRMs

- PRM methods merely reconstructs the input-output distribution.
- FRMs map input to output – i.e., predict properly

Plot: Truth ($\bar{\Sigma}_{DNS}^*$) Vs Prediction ($\bar{\Sigma}_{NN}^*$)

Conclusion:

- **Field regression models** showed **robust** performance across conditions.
- **Similar** patterns in prediction across different PRMs → **Inherent limitations** of ML models trained with **local data**.
- Major limitation found in **leaner flames**.

Future work:

- Evaluate online performance → i.e., coupled with LES solvers.
- Include other data driven methods like symbolic regression.

Thank you

References

- [1] V. Coulon, J. Gaucherand, V. Xing, D. Laera, C. Lapeyre, T. Poinsot, Direct numerical simulations of methane, ammonia-hydrogen and hydrogen turbulent premixed flames, *Combustion and Flame* 256 (2023) 112933
- [2] B. Savard, E. R. Hawkes, K. Aditya, H. Wang, J. H. Chen, Regimes of premixed turbulent spontaneous ignition and deflagration under gas-turbine reheat combustion conditions, *Combustion and Flame* 208 (2019) 402–419.